

Studies in Furan Derivatives: Part V.* Syntheses of some Furocoumarins

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Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate and methyl 5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate on formylation furnished the 7-formyl and 4-formyl derivative respectively. These have been utilized for the synthesis of furocoumarin derivatives by the application of Perkin and Knoevenagel condensation. Furocoumarin derivatives have been also prepared by the Pechmann condensation of ethyl acetoacetate with methyl 6-hydroxy 3-methylcoumarilate and methyl 4-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate. The structures of the furocoumarins obtained have been proved by degrading them to the compounds of known structures.

Some of the earlier workers¹⁻² found it difficult to synthesise furocoumarins by the Pechmann reaction on hydroxybenzofurans and they synthesised these by the Pechmann reaction on hydroxycoumarans and subsequent dehydrogenation. Some of the later workers³ have, however, been able to successfully carry out Pechmann reaction on hydroxybenzofurans. The difficulty in the syntheses of furocoumarins from benzofurans may probably be due to the high reactivity of the 2-position in benzofurans. It was therefore, thought of interest to see whether the furocoumarins could be synthesised by starting with hydroxybenzofurans with a group at 2-position which could be easily removed later on. Further, some of the hydroxybenzofurans on formylation afford 2-formyl derivatives⁴. It was therefore, thought of interest to see whether formylation in the benzenoid part could be achieved by formylating hydroxybenzofurans in which the 2-position is blocked by a group which could be easily removed later on. These formyl derivatives could be further utilised for syntheses of furocoumarins by Perkin and Knoevenagel reaction.

Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate⁵ when heated with hexamine in acetic acid gave a formyl derivative to which methyl 7-formyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate structure has been assigned. On Perkin acetylation it gave furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin (I) which was also obtained by the esterification of the known furo-2'-carboxy-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin⁶ as seen by direct comparison with an authentic specimen. This incidentally proved the structure of the above formyl derivative. The same formyl derivative on Knoevenagel condensation with ethyl malonate furnished ethyl furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin-3-carboxylate which was hydrolysed to the dicarboxylic acid and the acid then decarboxylated to the known furo-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin⁶ as seen by direct comparison with an authentic specimen.

*Part IV, *This Journal*, this issue.

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2. E Spath and M. Pailer, *Ber.*, 1936, **69B**, 767.
3. K. A. Thaker, *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 721.
4. R. T. Foster, A. Robertson and A. Bushra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 2254.
5. V. S. Salvi and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 135.
6. K. N. Trivedi and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 562.

Methyl 5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate⁷ when heated with hexamine in acetic acid gave a formyl derivative to which methyl 4-formyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate structure has been assigned on the basis of the N M R data.

High resolution N M R study was made on a Varian Spectrometer at 56.445 MC/S and the spectrum is shown in fig. 1. The spectrum of this compound was taken in CDCl_3 . The assignments of the various lines are also shown in the figure. The chemical shifts are reported relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard. In this spectrum, the presence of one CH_3 , one COOCH_3 group, two aromatic protons and one CHO along with one OH group is indicated. The two aromatic protons show a coupling of 10.2 c/s and hence it can be concluded that they are placed in the ortho position with respect to each other. The presence of the OH group at -12.94 ppm in such a dilute solution shows that there is an intramolecular hydrogen bonding in this compound like that in salicylaldehyde.

FIG. 1

On Perkin acetylation the 4-formyl derivative gave a product to which furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3'-methyl-4', 5'-5,6-coumarin structure has been assigned. This was further hydrolysed and decarboxylated to furo-3'-methyl-4', 5'-5, 6-coumarin (II). The 4-formyl derivative on Knoevenagel condensation with diethyl malonate furnished a product which has been assigned ethyl furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3'-methyl-4', 5'-5, 6-coumarin-3-carboxylate structure. This was hydrolysed and decarboxylated to the above described furo-3'-methyl-4', 5'-5, 6-coumarin.

Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate on Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of sulphuric acid gave a mixture of furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-5, 6-coumarin and furo-2'-carboxy-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-5, 6-coumarin. The ester was hydrolysed by alkali to the corresponding acid, which on decarboxylation gave the known furo-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-5, 6-coumarin⁸ as seen by direct comparison.

Methyl 4-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate required for Pechmann condensation was prepared by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-6-methoxyacetophenone⁹ with ethyl bromomalonate and hydrolysis of the intermediate product obtained to 4-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid. It was esterified and then demethylated. The structure of this product was proved by brominating the methoxy ester and subsequent hydrolysis to the known 7-bromo-4-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid¹⁰ as seen by direct comparison with an authentic specimen.

7. Part IV *This Journal*, this issue.

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9. W. Baker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 956.

10. S. S. Lele, R. J. Parikh and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1953, 30, 610.

The hydroxyester on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in sulphuric acid gave a mixture of furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-7, 8-coumarin (III) and the corresponding acid. The latter on decarboxylation with copper and quinoline gave the known furo-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-7,8-coumarin¹¹ as seen by direct comparison with an authentic specimen. The above acid was also prepared by condensing 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with ethyl bromomalonate and then hydrolysis of the ester obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Methyl 7-formyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate: Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1 g.) and hexamine (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) were heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. Hydrochloric acid (10 ml., 1 : 1) was then added and the heating continued for further 1/2 hr. The product obtained on extraction with ether crystallised from glacial acetic acid in needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 61.90; H, 4.61. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.54; H, 4.30%).

Methyl ether: Prepared by refluxing the above ester with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone for 15 min. when crystallised from acetic acid gave m.p. 197-98°. (Found: C, 63.28; H, 5.01. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.90; H, 4.87%).

2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the methyl ether: Prepared by mixing the above methyl ether with 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in hot acetic acid when crystallised from glacial acetic acid gave m.p. 261-62°. (Found: N, 12.63. $C_{19}H_{16}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.08%).

Furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3'-methyl-5', 4'5,-6-coumarin: A mixture of methyl 7-formyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.5 g.), acetic anhydride (0.7 g.) and fused sodium acetate (0.5 g.) was heated for 8 hr. at 180° in an oil bath. The reaction mixture was then poured in cold water and the product which separated was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 227°; yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 65.11; H, 3.72. $C_{14}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 65.12; H, 3.90%).

*All the m.p.s. are uncorrected.

11. D. B. Limaye, *Ber.*, 1932, **26**, 375.

The same furocoumarin was obtained when furo-2'-carboxy-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin (0.5 g.), prepared according to Trivedi and Sethna⁶, was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (0.5 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) in acetone (20 ml.) for 4 hr. on a steam bath.

Ethyl furo-2'-carboxymethoxy-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin-3-carboxylate: Methyl 7-formyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.32 g.) was mixed with diethyl malonate (0.16 g.). A few drops of pyridine and piperidine were added and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 36 hr. It was then added to dilute hydrochloric acid and the product which separated when crystallised from glacial acetic acid gave m.p. 215-16°; yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 61.67; H, 4.21. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 61.82; H, 4.27%).

Furo-2',3-dicarboxy-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin: The above ester (0.5 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 15 ml.) for 5 min. on a steam bath and then kept at room temperature for 90 min. The product obtained on acidification on crystallisation from acetic acid gave m.p. 340° (decomp.). (Found: C, 57.47; H, 3.20: analysed after drying in vacuum at 120° for 2 hr. $C_{14}H_8O_7$ requires C, 58.33; H, 2.77%).

The above acid (0.2 g.) was refluxed gently with copper (0.1 g.) and quinoline (5 ml.) for 5 min. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and added to dilute hydrochloric acid. The product which separated was crystallised from dilute alcohol. M.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of furo-3'-methyl-5',4'-5,6-coumarin was 134°.

Methyl 4-formyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate: Methyl 5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1 g.) and hexamine (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) were heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. Hydrochloric acid (10 ml., 1:1) was then added and heating continued for further 30 min. The product which separated crystallised from alcohol in needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 194°. (Found: C, 61.71; H, 4.33. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.54; H, 4.30%).

Methyl ether: Prepared by refluxing the above ester with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone for 30 min. was crystallised from dilute acetic acid. M.p. 161-62°. (Found: C, 62.90; H, 4.89. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.90; H, 4.87%).

2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone: Prepared by mixing methyl 4-formyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in hot acetic acid when crystallised from glacial acetic acid gave m.p. 282°. (Found: N, 14.04. $C_{18}H_{14}O_8N_4$ requires N, 13.53%).

Furo-2'-carboxymethoxy-3-methyl-4',5'-5,6-coumarin: A mixture of methyl-4-formyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.5 g.), acetic anhydride (0.7 g.) and fused sodium acetate (0.5 g.) was heated for 8 hr. at 180° in an oil bath. The reaction mixture was then poured in cold water and the product which separated crystallised from acetic acid. M.p. 242°; yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 65.36; H, 3.92; $C_{14}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 65.12; H, 3.96%).

Furo-2'-carboxy-3'-methyl-4',5'-5,6-coumarin: The above ester (1 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 20 ml.) for 30 min. on a steam bath. The product obtained on acidification on crystallisation from acetic acid gave m.p. 343° (Found: C, 63.89; H, 3.16; analysed after drying in vacuum at 120° for 2 hr. $C_{13}H_8O_5$ requires C, 63.93; H, 3.28%).

Furo-3'-methyl-4', 5'-5, 6-coumarin: The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed gently with copper (0.2 g.) and quinoline (10 ml.) for 10 min. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and dilute hydrochloric acid was added to it. The product which separated crystallised from dilute acetic acid. M.p. 175-76°; yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 71.65; H, 3.96. $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires C, 72.00; H, 4.00%).

Ethyl furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3'-methyl-4', 5'-5, 6-coumarin-3-carboxylate: Methyl 4-formyl-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.2 g.) was mixed with diethyl malonate (0.16 g.) and a few drops of pyridine and piperidine were added. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 36 hr. and then added to dilute hydrochloric acid. The product which separated on crystallisation from dilute acetic acid gave m.p. 192°. (Found: C, 62.31; H, 4.12. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 61.82; H, 4.24%).

Furo-2'-dicarboxy-3'-methyl-4',5'-5, 6-coumarin: The above ester (0.5 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (10%; 15 ml.) for 10 min. on a steam bath and kept at room temperature for 1 hr. The product obtained on acidification crystallised from acetic acid. M.p. 355° (decomp.). (Found: C, 58.13; H, 3.22; analysed after drying in vacuum at 120° for 4 hr. $C_{14}H_8O_7$ requires C, 58.33; H, 2.77%).

The above acid was refluxed gently with copper (0.1 g.) and quinoline (8 ml.) for 10 min. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was filtered and added to dilute hydrochloric acid. The product which separated on crystallisation from dilute acetic acid gave m.p. 175°; yield 0.2 g. Mixed m.p. with furo-3'-methyl-4',5'-5, 6-coumarin described above was not depressed.

(A) *Furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3',4-dimethyl-5', 4'-5, 6-coumarin* and (B) *Furo-2'-carboxy-3',4-dimethyl-5', 4'-5, 6-coumarin*: Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (2 g.) in ethyl acetoacetate (3 g.) was added slowly to sulphuric acid (80%; 50 ml.) and the reaction mixture kept at room temperature for 48 hr. It was then added to ice cold water and the separated product was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution (10%; 20 ml.). The product (A) insoluble in alkali was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 217°. (Found: C, 65.71; H, 4.19. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.17; H, 4.44%). The product (B) soluble in alkali was precipitated by adding dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 312°. (Found: C, 65.21; H, 4.33. $C_{14}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 65.12; H, 3.96%).

The same acid (B) was also obtained by hydrolysis of ester (A) (1 g.) by heating with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (10%; 20 ml.) on a steam bath for 30 min.

The above acid (0.5 g.) was heated with copper (0.1 g.) and quinoline (2 ml.) for 40 min. and the reaction mixture was filtered and added to dilute hydrochloric acid. The product obtained on ether extraction was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 198°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of furo-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-5, 6-coumarin prepared according to Chudgar and Shah⁸ was not depressed.

4-Methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid: 2-Hydroxy-6-methoxy-acetophenone (1.5 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromomalonate (2.4 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in ethyl methyl ketone for 6 hr. on a steam bath. On evaporation of the solvent the reaction mixture was added to water. The oily intermediate product (1 g.) obtained on

ether extraction was heated on a steam bath with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (10 %; 20 ml.) for 1 hr. The solid obtained on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 238°; yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 64.53; H, 5.13. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.07; H, 4.89%).

Methyl 4-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate: 4-Methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid (0.2 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (0.12 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.4 g.) in acetone (10 ml.) for 4 hr. The product obtained on working up as before on crystallisation from alcohol gave m.p. 83-84°. (Found: C, 65.43; H, 5.22. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.44; H, 5.49%).

Methyl 4-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate: The above ester (1 g.) mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) was refluxed in dry benzene on a steam bath for 4 hr. On cooling, the benzene was removed and the complex was decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid. The separated product was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 178-79°. (Found: C, 63.91; H, 4.46. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.07; H, 4.89%).

Methyl 7-bromo-4-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate: Methyl-4-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml.) was treated with bromine (0.8 g.) in acetic acid (8 ml.). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 hr. The separated product crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 154°. (Found: Br, 26.77. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4$ Br requires Br, 26.75%).

The above bromo ester (1 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (10 %; 20 ml.) for 1 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 270°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-bromo-4-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid prepared according to Lele, Parikh and Sethna¹⁰ was not depressed.

(A) *Furo-2'-carbomethoxy-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-7, 8-coumarin* and (B) *Furo-2'-carboxy-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-7, 8-coumarin*: Methyl 4-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (2 g.) in ethyl acetoacetate (3 g.) was added slowly to sulphuric acid (80%; 50 ml.) and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr. It was then added to ice cold water and the separated product was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution (10%; 20 ml.) The ester (A), insoluble in alkali, was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 231-32°. (Found: C, 66.54; H, 4.07. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.17; H, 4.44%). The acid (B), soluble in alkali, was precipitated by adding dilute hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 312-13°. (Found: C, 64.82; H, 3.55; analysed after drying at 110° in vacuum. $C_{14}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 65.12; H, 3.90%).

The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with copper (0.1 g.) and quinoline (2 ml.) for 1 hr. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was filtered and added to dilute hydrochloric acid. The product obtained on crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave m.p. 176°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of furo-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-7, 8-coumarin prepared according to Limaye¹¹ was not depressed.

Furo-2'-carboethoxy-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-7, 8-coumarin: 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2.2 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromomalonate (2.4 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) in ethyl methyl ketone (50 ml.) for 6 hr. on a steam bath.

On evaporation of the solvent the reaction mixture was added to water and the separated product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 188-89°; yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 67.67; H, 4.61. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 67.12; H, 4.93%).

The above ester (1 g.) was heated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (10%; 20 ml.) on a steam bath for 1 hr. and the reaction mixture acidified. The product obtained on crystallisation from acetic acid gave m.p. 312-13°. Mixed m.p. with furo-2'-carboxy-3', 4-dimethyl-5', 4'-7, 8- coumarin described above was not depressed.

Our grateful thanks are due to Dr. C. R. Kanekar of the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bombay, for the NMR data and helpful discussions regarding its interpretation. One of us (V.S.S.) thanks the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, for the award of a Junior Fellowship.

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Received, August 3, 1967.